

The Effectiveness of Home Industry Behavior on the Welfare of the People in Makassar City

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Industrial development in the era of globalization has resulted in increased business opportunities. The current business environment has undergone many changes such as advanced technology, the product life cycle is getting shorter, the complexity of production is increasing, thus causing significant modifications in the accounting practices of the management of an enterprise. Today's economic world has developed so rapidly that it is characterized by advances in science and technology. This results in a high level of competition between companies in order to meet the needs of the community as consumers of the products produced by the company. Developments in this increasingly modern era, the government must be fast in building a strong economy, one of which is through home industry because home industry is a form of activity in the business world and as a form of people's economy that has the potential to develop the people's economy and has an impact on improving the national economy. Home Industry is currently developing quite rapidly in Indonesia, so the existence of home industry can help the government in alleviating poverty and reducing unemployment. Home Industry in Indonesia is quite stable and able to maintain a balance of conditions when the economic crisis comes. Home Industry activities are one of the main components in the development of the local economy. Its existence is very necessary in Makassar City, because rural industries in general can be characterized by small-scale industries. In rural industrial processes, industry in rural areas is indispensable in an effort to increase added value which in turn can improve the economy. Growth Home Industry is an industry that has an important role in supporting the pace of regional economic growth, and the development of Home Industry continues to grow in line with development development. The food industry is one of the most popular and developed business opportunities by producers, because food is a primary need. When compared to other needs, such as houses, clothes, cars, electronics, and so on, food is a basic human need where humans will not be able to live or not be peaceful in their lives if their food needs are not met. As a result of the development of this industry, food and beverage franchise businesses began to rise in Indonesia. This condition has certainly caused an increase in competition among producers, both local producers and international producers.

The history of the development of the industrial sector in development in Indonesia is inseparable from the role and existence of the small industry sector and folk crafts, which historically its presence is much earlier than the modern industries in Indonesia today. Although the income from the home industry in general is still relatively low or still relatively small in income, the role of home

This industry itself is very important in improving the economy, compared to the large industries in Indonesia today but the home industry's existence cannot be ignored in the economic downturn in Indonesia. Home industry is known as an additional source of income for the community and also as a support for agricultural activities which are the basic livelihood of most rural communities. Because of the role of home industry, the development of home industry has an important meaning in an effort to reduce the level of poverty in the city of Makassar. To meet these needs, humans carry out various business activities. The running of a business cannot be separated from the importance of a strategy to be able to maintain a competitive advantage in order to increase income in order to survive decently. By developing its products and improving the quality provided to each consumer. For this reason, the home industry should provide guarantees for the quality of its production, of the aspects that must be met by every company, especially in the home industry business.

A. Problem Formulation

Based on the background that has been described, the main problems of this paper are:

- How is the behavior of the traditional cake industry home in makassar city
- What are the advantages and disadvantages of traditional cake industry home activities in the city of Makassar
- How is the strategy for developing traditional home industry activities to be able to improve the welfare of the people of Makassar city

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Basic Concepts of Behavioral Theory*

a) Definition of Behavior

Behavior is a set of actions or actions of a person in responding to something and then making it a habit because of the existence of believed value. Human behavior is essentially an action or activity from humans both observed and unobserved by human interaction with its context manifested in the form of knowledge, attitudes, and actions. Behavior more rationally can be interpreted as a response of the organism or a person towards stimuli from outside the subject. This response is formed two kind of i.e. passive form and active form where passive form is response internal i.e. what occurs in man and is not directly visible from others while the active form is when the behavior can be observed Directly. Behavior is basically goal-oriented and motivated by the desire to acquire a specific goal. Behavior is an action or response in the environment to something. Of course, many experts also have their own views on the definition of this behavior, here is a list of understandings according to experts in their fields:

- According to the American Encyclopaedia, behavior is defined as an action and reaction of an organism to its environment, this means that a new behavior will be realized when something is needed to cause a response called a stimulus, thus a certain stimulus will produce a certain behavior as well.
- According to Benjamin Bloom in Adventus, et al (2019) a psychologist, This behavior occurs through the process of having a stimulus to the organism and then the organism responds, then Skinner's theory is called "S-O-R" or Stimulus Organism Response. This area is carried out for the benefit of its educational purposes it develops or improves all three behavioral domains, consisting of : the cognitive domain (cognitive domain) affective domain (affective domain), and the psychomotor realm (psychomotor domain).

b) Definition of Home Industry

In the midst of a crisis, it is stated that the household industry is a business unit or company on a small scale engaged in a certain industry. Sumaatmadja expresses industry in two senses, namely in the broad and narrow sense. In a broad sense, industry is all human activities utilizing natural resources, while in the narrow sense industry is an economic activity that processes raw materials into finished or semi-finished goods (manufacturing industry).

According to Muliawan Home Industry is a small-scale company, usually this company only uses one or two houses as production, administration and marketing centers at the same time at the same time. When viewed from the business capital and the amount of labor absorbed, it is certainly less than that of large companies in general.

According to Husnan and Syahdan in their journal (2019: 5) home industry is an effort to find benefits or benefits of the physical form of an item so that it can be used to meet needs and be done at home. In this sense it includes also handicraft activities. So that home industry can be interpreted as an effort to produce where there is a change in the shape or nature of an item. Home industry activities are generally the work of farmers and villagers, which has the meaning of an additional source of income. One of the goals of industrialization of rural areas is to develop the economic activities of the area, and in an effort to develop small industries and folk crafts. In industrial development, the role of the government is very large in its benefits. For this reason, direction, coaching, capital assistance, training and development assistance in the industrial sector are highly expected.

According to BPS companies or industrial ventures can be grouped into four categories based on the amount of labor used from the company in question include:

- Small industry or household crafts, which is an industry whose workforce is 1-5 people.
- Small industries, namely industries whose number of workers is between 5-19 workers.
- Medium industry, which is an industry whose total workforce is between 20-99 people.
- Large industries, that is, industries whose number of workers is between 100 or more workers per company. To find out more about the meaning of this home industry, then to foster the development of this kind of home industry which is usually done in rural areas, at least it requires

c) Definition of economic well-being

Public Welfare The level of well-being can be defined as an aggregate condition of the satisfaction of individuals. That basic understanding leads to a complex understanding divided into two arenas of debate. The first is what the scope of the substance of well-being is second is how the intensity of the substance can be represented aggregate. Well-being is a certain amount of satisfaction that a person obtains from the results of consuming the income received. However, the level of well-being itself is something of a relative nature because depending on the amount of satisfaction obtained from the results of consuming the income. Well-being is a certain amount of satisfaction that a person gets from the results of consuming the income received, but the level of welfare itself is something relative because it depends on the amount of satisfaction obtained from the results of consuming that income. The interrelationship between the concept of well-being and the concept of needs. The definition of prosperous itself is a human condition in which the people are in a state of prosperity, in good health, and peace, so to achieve that condition the person needs an effort according to his abilities. Well-being is a measuring point for society which means that it has been in a prosperous state.

The term empowerment in the Oxford English Dictionary is a translation of the word empower which contains two meanings: (i) to give power to (give power, transfer power or delegate authority to another party), (ii) to give ability to, enable (effort to give ability). Etymologically empowerment comes from the word daya which means strength or ability. Departing from this understanding, empowerment can be interpreted as a process towards being empowered, or a process to obtain power / strength / ability from parties who have power to parties who are less or not yet empowered. Empowerment in the economic sector is an effort to build (community) power by encouraging, motivating, and raising awareness of its economic potential and striving to develop it. Community empowerment is the basic element that allows a society to survive. In a dynamic sense, that is, developing oneself and achieving progress. Community economic empowerment is strengthening the ownership of production factors, strengthening control of distribution and marketing, strengthening the community to get adequate salaries/wages, and strengthening the community to obtain information, knowledge and skills, which must be done in multi-aspects, both from the aspects of their own society, as well as aspects of their policies. Thus, the economic empowerment of the community in this study is a process to achieve certain goals, such as improving social welfare in order to strengthen its society from various aspects, especially the economy.

d) Definition of traditional cakes

Traditional cakes in addition to the main types of basic ingredients have the uniqueness of processing and serving traditional culinary which Most of the traditional culinary products are formulated and processed using traditional techniques such as cooked in bamboo, wrapped in banana leaves, serving techniques that require special skills so that they are interesting to be used as tourist attractions and activities, in addition to the taste of their own culinary products. The development of traditional cakes typical of Makassar is very diverse, abundant, and no less interesting than other tribes in Indonesia ranging from heavy food, snacks to fresh and healthy drinks (Qibtiya, 2019). Typical culinary is a cultural asset owned by the community that is very important to be preserved. Traditional culinary is always evolving with the times. As a result of these developments, traditional culinary began to be forgotten. Many young people do not know the diversity of traditional culinary in Indonesia, especially traditional cakes in the area where they live.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODS

Types of qualitative research through a phenomenological approach

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION

A. *Overview of Makassar City*

Makassar City, also known as Ujung Pandang, is one of the cities in the province of South Sulawesi that has its own uniqueness with its strategic position on the coastline which is the gateway to the eastern region of Indonesia. Geographically, Makassar City is located in the southwestern part of the province of South Sulawesi, namely at 5o 8' 6"19" South Latitude and 119o 24'17"38" East Longitude with an altitude that varies between 1-25 meters above sea level. Makassar City is a flat coastal area with a slope of 0-5 degrees to the west, flanked by two river estuaries, namely rivers. Tallo which empties into the northern part of the city and the Jeneberang river which empties into the south of the city. The total area of the city of Makassar amounts to approximately 175.77 km² of land and includes 11 islands in the Makassar strait with a water area of approximately 100 Km². Makassar City area consists of 14 sub-district areas with 1143 urban areas, 974 RW and 4,827 RT. The boundaries of Makassar City are: the north bordering Maros Regency; to the East it borders Maros County; to the South with Gowa County; and to the West with the Makassar Strait.

Food is a basic (basic) need that is very important for human life both physiologically, psychologically, socially and anthropologically. Food has always been linked to human efforts to maintain its survival and health on earth. Food can also be the identity of a nation or civilization. Food is very much variety and types, from traditional to modern. In Indonesia, there are many kinds of archipelago specialties or what we often call culinary specialties. The diversity of ethnic groups of different cultures, languages, religions, and customs is what creates a variety of cuisines, foods, and drinks that are characteristic of each region. Culinary is one of the main attractions in this country. In every region in the country has special foods, of which there are very many types that are spread throughout the archipelago. Traditional food is food consumed by a certain society with a distinctive taste. One of the areas that is very famous for its snacks is Makassar City. Ironically, in the Makassar City area, there are a lot of fast food snacks and cafes, hotels and tourist attractions that no longer serve traditional food which is the legacy of the ancestors of the Makassar tribe. The growing number of tourists in Makassar City should be an important concern for the government and business actors to introduce more deeply related to the traditional cakes of the city of Makassar. Snack foods or traditional cakes are classified as types of wet cakes. These foods are commonly called snacks that can be used as an alternative snack. It is usually eaten in the morning or evening. The cake is generally tender, soft, and doesn't last long (it only lasts a few days). Usually made from wheat flour, sago, sugar, some are even made from coconut milk or glutinous rice. Traditional snack food in Makassar City has many types, for example Pisang ijo, Pisang epe, dodor, baje, teng - teng, beruas, baje banding, otere otere and others. Traditional cakes can be considered to have many benefits such as causing interest in curiosity so that they want to shop to be used as ingredients for fruits or snacks when you want to visit an mpat or also just want to try traditional cakes from the city of Makassar. Through the traditional cake home industry, it has a good impact in terms of improving the family economy. This is evidenced by a fairly good increase in income that is able to meet the needs of clothing, food, housing, health, education and social. The achievement of economic welfare when these needs are met, so that it will indirectly influence changes in the standard of living for the better. Traditional culinary is one of the attractions of tourists both in terms of domestic and international who visit the area. The traditional culinary of Makassar city has a diversity of traditional culinary heritage that is abundant and no less interesting than other tribes in Indonesia and deserves to be preserved. The culinary wealth of Makassar city includes first courses, desserts, to fresh and healthy drinks. From the discussion above, traditional cakes need innovation or new flavors to increase interest and selling points.

B. Behavior of the traditional cake home industry in the city of Makassar

Home Industry is a business house of goods products or small companies. It is said to be a small enterprise because this type of economic activity is centered at home. Home Industry can mean home industry, because it includes small family-run businesses at home. In general, the actors of economic activities based at home are the family itself by inviting people around them as employees. Although on a small scale, this economic activity indirectly opens up jobs for relatives or neighbors. Along with economic developments, the goals of home industry companies have also experienced a turnaround that was previously only centralized in trying to achieve the greatest market benefits but has so far expanded to other economic goals related to the organization of companies that develop in the economy. In every company, both small and large businesses have goals and objectives. The general goal of the company is to create and distribute the goods or services needed by society economically and efficiently for profit. The labor aspect or better known as human resources, the longer its existence becomes more important for the success of the company.

People's lifestyle is an activity that can be observed directly or indirectly, human behavior tends to be arbitrary and almost most of the changes in society occur naturally. People's lifestyles are always changing so that they can influence a business that does not keep up with the times, along with the development of civilization and the life of modern and global society today, as well as the support of information systems that are developing rapidly beyond the barriers of administrative and cultural areas of the community so that impressions from the media and electronics have participated in disseminating and providing information to the public in getting to know, marketing and carrying out economic activities from the potential of traditional culinary so that it has become the lifestyle of modern people. The taste of traditional cakes that are very exotic has given a special place to culinary tourism enthusiasts who are growing very rapidly. If so far culinary has only been a complement to tourist travel activities, then currently culinary has become one of the tourist activities that has become a special attraction for tourists to travel. A very distinctive and exotic taste is influenced by the use of natural and fresh ingredients, seasonings, spices and concoctions so that traditional culinary is also healthier compared to fast food culinary that is widely sold by international restaurants. Traditional culinary is a cultural identity of the community which is very thick with processing and serving at certain times and needs such as linkages with cultural processions and beliefs and is held at certain times such as thanksgiving and wedding parties. Thus, the approach to traditional culinary cannot be separated from the culture of the people of Makassar city. The potential of traditional cakes in Makassar city has a very large opportunity to develop, especially if it is associated with tourism which can not only trigger visiting interest, regional and community income, job opportunities and business opportunities, but also as a medium in preserving community culture, forming a healthier and smarter society, and as a promotional medium for the city of Makassar in attracting tourists.

In addition to traditional culinary opportunities that are very potential, some of the obstacles that are also faced in the development of traditional culinary in makassar city are people's lifestyles that tend to be modern, with a stigma built on people's thoughts and actions that modernity is to follow the lifestyle of the global community, including consuming fast food culinary in restaurants or hotels with more luxurious physical facilities.

C. Advantages and disadvantages of traditional cake home industry activities in the city of Makassar

a) Advantages of traditional cake home industry activities in makassar city

- They can get standard recipes in an easier way by accessing several sources of information through existing technology.
- Creating jobs, the existence of home industry has also played a role in shaping the mothers or children of business owners into productive human beings because they have been able to take advantage of their free time to help increase production productivity and do not reduce the possibility of inviting the surrounding community to participate in working to run their business.
- Traditional Culture in the form of various types of pastries or traditional snacks. Traditional Makassar cakes were previously only used for traditional wedding purposes that served a variety of traditional wet cakes to entertain invited guests, currently it has developed into a business product with a varied look and taste and is sold in modern stores and as souvenirs.
- The potential of traditional cakes as an attraction for the city of Makassar as a tourism destination. The characteristics of traditional cakes as a culinary tourism attraction of the city of Makassar show that the culinary of the city of Makassar is largely a cultural assimilation with the immigrant tourist community.

b) Weaknesses of traditional cake industry home activities in Makassar city

- Traditional cakes are cakes whose recipes are down and down and traditional cakes are mostly processed by parents, the processing of traditional cakes tends to be long using traditional utensils.
- Some traditional cake industry homes do not yet have financial reports in order to easily evaluate the business, and for the implementation of management functions should be improved again.
- This low appreciation of traditional culinary is more likely to be caused by the condition of the point of sale that provides traditional culinary, product standardization, eating and serving procedures that tend to be conventional with the arrangement of alakadar, as well as promotion and marketing which is still very limited. This further cornered the traditional culinary position to compete with fast food that was marketed more professionally by the industry and international scale companies.
- Limited knowledge of traditional cake business actors in Makassar to manage their business professionally, for example in terms of packaging. In general, the packaging of traditional snacks in Makassar City is still untouched by good packaging even though packaging is one of the added values of a product.
- The traditional home industry of Makassar City actually has quite good prospects to be developed, it's just that business actors lack knowledge of good business management or too many considerations in terms of building marketing partnerships and doubts about dealing with bureaucracy and regulations that they consider complicated.
- There is still a lack of access to financing institutions due to ignorance or unable to meet the requirements set by financial institutions, resulting in traditional snack entrepreneurs always stuck in the classic problem of limited capital to develop their business.

c) How is the strategy for developing traditional cake home industry activities to be able to improve the welfare of the people of Makassar city

The strategies used in building economic welfare in Makassar City are

- Education and training, this approach strategy emphasizes the importance of a learning process to increase community empowerment, by increasing the independence, ability, and empowerment of the community to achieve the desired goals.
- As an attraction for culinary tourism in Makassar, through various efforts, namely the implementation of culinary competitions at various events between traditional cake home industries, thus encouraging products and marketing in various types of businesses including hotels and restaurants, as well as conducting promotions on various media including social media.
- Conducting guidance and guidance to cake snack business actors

- traditional typical of the city of Makassar in terms of standardization of quality, quality and hygiene of products. In addition, it is necessary to teach traditional cake business actors in Makassar city to carry out attractive and safe packaging.
- The need for government participation, especially the Makassar City Government, in inventorying traditional cake snacks typical of the city of Makassar as an effort to maintain the sustainability and sustainability of traditional snack production so that it can be widely known. In addition, the inventory aims to select what traditional makassar cake snacks have good prospects to be further developed professionally.
- So that traditional products cakes typical of the city of Makassar can still exist and increasing the competitiveness of the traditional cake snack business in Makassar city, which is generally a household industry, needs guidance on more efficient and effective business management so that this snack business does not only become a home business.
- Ease of access to financing is also one of the efforts to developing a traditional cake snack business in Makassar City, because business capital is still a classic problem that is always complained by traditional cake entrepreneurs in Makassar City, which is still a household industry.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and analysis that the author carried out, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The traditional cake home industry business in Makassar City has implemented a management function, namely
 - planning: planning the raw materials to be produced, capital for the cangek / gendar cracker business, equipment used at the time of production, and production targets when marketing products.
 - Organizing: the presence of an organizational structure of the division of labor.
 - Implementation of production: carrying out from pre-established planning and organizing.
 - Control: the existence of supervision and motivation for employees as well.
 - Control of the production process.

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